

Additional file 6: Table S3. *D. melanogaster* strains.

Genotype	Reference
<i>Oregon-R-P2</i>	RRID:BDSC_2376
<i>w¹¹¹⁸</i>	RRID:BDSC_3605
<i>Canton-S</i>	RRID:BDSC_64349
<i>ato¹</i>	[122]; RRID:BDSC_25779
<i>Df(3R)p13</i>	RRID:BDSC_1943
<i>amos³</i>	[29]
<i>UAS-mCD8:GFP</i>	RRID:BDSC_5137
<i>UAS-CD4:tdTomato</i>	RRID:BDSC_35841
<i>Or67d^{Gal4#1}</i>	[123]
<i>Or88a-mCD8:GFP</i>	RRID:BDSC_52644
<i>Or83c-mCD8:GFP</i>	RRID:BDSC_52639
<i>Or2a-mCD8:GFP</i>	RRID:BDSC_52611
<i>Or47b-Gal4</i>	RRID:BDSC_9983
<i>nompA-Gal4</i>	[50, 124]
<i>ASE5-Gal4</i>	RRID:BDSC_93029
<i>lush-Gal4</i>	[88]
<i>Cre (recombinase)</i>	RRID:BDSC_851
<i>{Act5C-Cas9.P.RFP-}ZH-2A w[118]</i> <i>Lig[169]</i>	RRID:BDSC_58492
<i>Osi8¹</i>	<i>This work</i>
<i>Osi8^{1-DsRed}</i>	<i>This work</i>
<i>Osi8-Gal4</i>	<i>This work</i>
<i>UAS-Osi8</i>	<i>This work</i>
<i>UAS-SS:EGFP:Osi8</i>	<i>This work</i>
<i>Act5C-Gal4,UAS-Dcr-2</i>	RRID:BDSC_3954, RRID:BDSC_24651
<i>Osi8-15591R-1 (UAS-Osi8^{RNAi}) (chr. II)</i>	NIG-FLY